

Kinetics of Nickel(II) Ion and Cobalt(II) Ion Catalysed Hydroxamic Acid Formation from Formic Acid

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The Kinetics of Ni(II) ion catalysed formation of hydroxamic acid from formic acid and hydroxylamine revealed to be first order each with respect to formic acid, hydroxylamine and Ni(II) ion concentration. Cobalt(II) ion is comparable with Ni(II) ion in its catalytic efficiency, but its catalytic effect is weaker than that of the Ni(II) ion. The activation parameters have been evaluated and a probable mechanism has been suggested.

As a special type of amide, hydroxamic acid can be formed by the reaction of hydroxylamine with carboxylic acid in neutral and acidic medium^{1,2}. Working with aliphatic carboxylic acids and aliphatic amines, Morawetz and Otaki³ were able to detect amide formation in aqueous solution, although 'activation' of an acyl group (by converting into an ester, acid anhydride, thiol ester, acyl phosphate, etc.) is usually considered to be a prerequisite to amide formation⁴. The present paper reports the kinetics of the reaction of hydroxylamine with formic acid catalysed by Ni(II) ion and Co(II) ion in aqueous solutions.

Experimental

Material and method: Ferric chloride reagent (0.15 M) was prepared by dissolving 40.545 g of ferric chloride hexahydrate and 50 ml conc. HCl in water to make 1 litre. All other chemicals were of reagent grade.

Kinetic measurement: The kinetics of hydroxamic acid formation was studied by preparing various sets of reaction mixture. In each case appropriate aliquots of reactant solutions were mixed in a reaction flask and pH of the solution was adjusted with strong NaOH or HCl solutions. Portions (3 ml) of the reaction mixture, thus prepared, were sealed in glass ampoules and placed in a thermostated water bath to initiate the reaction. Ampoules were removed at recorded time intervals and the reaction was quickly quenched by immersing the ampoules in an ice bath. One ml content of an ampoule was added to 20 ml ferric chloride reagent contained in a 25 ml volumetric flask. The absorbance due to ferric hydroxamate complex was measured at 530 nm by spectrophotometer 'Spekol'^{5,6}.

Results and Discussion

Ni(II) ion catalysed hydroxamic acid formation: The initial concentrations used for the study of Ni(II) ion catalysed formohydroxamic acid formation were formic acid 0.04 M, hydroxylamine hydrochloride 0.8 M and nickel chloride 0.04 M.

The order of reaction (n) calculated by van't Hoff differential method is found to be 1.0 with respect to formic acid (Table 1), 0.9 with respect to hydroxylamine (Table 2) and 0.75 with respect to nickel chloride (Table 3). The deviation from unity may be attributed to the complexity of the reaction.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING FORMIC ACID CONCENTRATION ON INITIAL REACTION RATE AT 90.5°
(NiCl₂) = 0.04 M; (NH₂OH.HCl) = 0.8 M;
pH = 5.25 (measured at 27°)

(Formic Acid) M	Initial rate V ₀ (M sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁴	n
0.02	1.90	1.0
0.03	2.85	1.0
0.04	3.80	1.0
0.06	5.94	

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING NH₂OH.HCl CONCENTRATION ON INITIAL REACTION RATE AT 90.5°
(HCOOH) = 0.04 M; (NiCl₂) = 0.04 M;
pH = 5.25 (measured at 27°)

(NH ₂ OH.HCl) M	Initial rate V ₀ (M sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁴	n
0.4	1.90	1.00
0.6	2.85	0.91
0.8	3.80	0.89
1.0	4.63	0.90
1.2	5.46	

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING NiCl₂ CONCENTRATION ON INITIAL REACTION RATE AT 90.5°
(HCOOH) = 0.04 M; (NH₂OH.HCl) = 0.8 M;
pH = 5.0 (measured at 27°)

(NiCl ₂) M	Initial rate V ₀ (M sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁴	n
0.04	3.92	
0.06	4.51	0.75
0.08	5.92	
0.10	6.41	0.81
0.12	7.86	0.75

Assuming the rate equation $V = k'(\text{HCOOH})_x(\text{NH}_2\text{OH})_y$, the apparent second order rate constant

k' can be calculated from initial rate measurements. The reaction was studied at different temperatures and the various activation parameters are reported in Table 4. The rate constant expression for the reaction of hydroxylamine with formic acid in the presence of Ni(II) ion can be expressed as

$$k = 1.2 \times 10^4 e^{-16610/RT} M^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH TEMPERATURE

(NiCl₂) = 0.04 M, (NH₂OH.HCl) = 0.8 M, (HCOOH) = 0.04 M, pH = 5.0 (measured at 27°)

Temperature (°C)	70	75	80	85	90
$k' \times 10^4 (M^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1})$	0.33	0.49	0.67	0.96	1.26

Activation parameters
 E_a = 16.6 ± 0.3 k cal/mole
 ΔS[‡] = -42.1 ± 0.2 e.u.
 ΔH[‡] = 15.9 ± 0.1 k cal/mole
 A = 1.3 × 10⁴ sec⁻¹

The pH rate profile (Fig 1[A]) for Ni(II) ion catalysed hydroxamic acid formation can be calculated by the equation (1).

$$v = k'_2 [\text{HCOOH}][\text{NH}_2\text{OH}][\text{H}^+] + k' [\text{HCOOH}][\text{NH}_2\text{OH}] + k_{\text{Ni}} [\text{HCOO}^-][\text{NH}_2\text{OH}][\text{Ni}^{2+}] \quad (1)$$

The first term corresponds to hydrogen ion catalysis whereas the second term involves no catalyst. However, the third term corresponds to Ni(II) ion catalysed reaction of hydroxylamine with the formate ion (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. pH rate profile for formohydroxamic acid formation at 90.5°.

[A] → [HCOOH] = 0.04 M; [NH₂OH.HCl] = 0.8 M, [NiCl₂] = 0.04 M.
 [B] → [HCOOH] = 0.04 M; [NH₂OH.HCl] = 0.8 M; [CoCl₂] = 0.04 M.
 [C] → [HCOOH] = 0.04 M; [NH₂OH.HCl] = 0.8 M.

Complexation of Ni(II) ion with hydroxylamine would decrease the electron density on the nitrogen atom of hydroxylamine, making it a poorer nucleophile. A catalytically favourable chelate complex involving formate ion may be formulated as under.

Formation of such a complex will make carbonyl carbon atom more electron deficient and therefore make it more susceptible to a nucleophilic attack.

Based on the kinetic data, the following probable mechanism for Ni(II) ion catalysed hydroxylaminolysis of formic acid is suggested.

Scheme-I
(Uncatalysed reaction)

Scheme-II
(Acid catalysed reaction)

Scheme-III
Ni(II) ion catalysed reaction

Cobalt(II) ion catalysed hydroxamic acid formation : The comparison of pH rate profile for Ni(II) ion and Co(II) ion catalysed (Fig. 1[A] and [B]) formation of hydroxamic acid reveals that Ni(II) ion is a better catalyst than Co(II) ion^{7,8}.

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